

KINEMATIK QO‘ZG‘ALISHLAR TA‘SIRIDAGI TO‘RTBURCHAK PLASTINKANING XUSUSIY CHASTOTALARINI ANIQLASH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu ishda kinematik qo‘zg‘alishlar ta‘siridagi qarama qarshi tomonlari qistirib mahkamlangan va qolgan ikki tomonlari erkin bo‘lgan to‘g‘ri to‘rtburchak shaklidagi plastinkaning xususiy chastotalarini aniqlash masalasi qaralgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: plastinka, chastota, qo‘zg‘alishlar, chegaraviy shartlar, tebranish formalari.

Kirish. Hozirda ilg‘or texnika va texnologiyalarning turli sohalaridagi mexanik sistemalar murakkab elementlarining tebranishlarini o‘rganish, jumladan bu sistemalar elementlarining xususiy chastotalarini aniqlash muhim masalalardan biri hisoblanadi.

[1–9] - ishlarda g‘ovakli materialdan tayyorlangan doiraviy plastinkaning erkin tebranishlari tahlil qilingan. Plastinka yupqa deb qabul qilinib, bo‘ylama deformatsiyalar hisobga olinmagan. Materialning g‘ovaklik xususiyatlari plastinka qalinligi bo‘yicha berilgan funksional qonuniyat asosida o‘zgaradi deb faraz qilingan. G‘ovaklarning taqsimlanishi va ularning siqiluvchanligi kabi parametrlarning xususiy chastota hamda kuchlanishlarga ta‘siri grafiklar yordamida ko‘rsatilgan. O‘zgaruvchan qalinlikka ega bo‘lgan doiraviy va halqasimon plastinkalarning tebranish chastotalarini aniqlash masalasi yechilgan. Xususiy chastotalarni ifodalovchi formulalar hosil qilingan. Chegaraviy shartlar hamda konsentrik halqa tayanch radiusining xususiy chastotalarga ta‘siri alohida o‘rganilgan.

Bugungi kunda kinematik qo‘zg‘alishlar ta‘siridagi qarama qarshi tomonlari qistirib mahkamlangan va qolgan ikki tomonlari erkin bo‘lgan to‘g‘ri to‘rtburchak shaklidagi plastinkaning xususiy chastotalarini aniqlash dolzarb hisoblanadi.

Material va metodlar. Kinematik qo‘zg‘alishlar ta‘siridagi qarama qarshi tomonlari qistirib mahkamlangan va qolgan ikki tomonlari erkin bo‘lgan to‘g‘ri to‘rtburchak shaklidagi plastinka xususiy chastotalarini aniqlash masalasini qaraymiz.

U holda bu xususiy tebranish formasini quyidagicha olamiz:

$$u_{ik}(x, y) = X_i(x)Y_k(y) = X_i(x)Y_i(y), \quad (1)$$

bunda

$$X_i(x) = A_1 \cosh(\alpha_i x) + A_2 \sinh(\alpha_i x) + A_3 \cos(\alpha_i x) + A_4 \sin(\alpha_i x), \quad (2)$$

$$Y_i(y) = A_5 \cosh(\beta_i y) + A_6 \sinh(\beta_i y) + A_7 \cos(\beta_i y) + A_8 \sin(\beta_i y), \quad (3)$$

$A_1, A_2, A_3, A_4, A_5, A_6$ – chegaraviy shartlardan aniqlanadigan koeffitsientlar; α_i va β_i **transsendent tenglama ildizlari**; x, y – plastinka tomonlari bo‘ylab yo‘nalgan o‘qlar.

Erkin tomonlari uchun α_i larni aniqlash imkonini beruvchi tenglamani hosil qilamiz.

$$\cosh(\alpha_i a) \cos(\alpha_i a) - 1 = 0, \quad (4)$$

bunda a – plastinka tomoni.

Bu tenglik bilan aniqlangan funksiyaning grafigi quyidagicha bo‘ladi:

1-rasm. (4) chastotani aniqlash imkonini beruvchi tenglama grafigi (a) va uning nollari (b,c)

1-rasmda (4) chastotani aniqlash imkonini beruvchi tenglama grafigi (a) va uning nollari (b,c) tasvirlangan. Bu garfikdan (4) tenglamani qanoatlantiruvchi $\alpha_i a$ ning noldan farqli dastlabki ikkita qiymatlarini quyidagicha aniqlash mumkin:

$$\alpha_i a = 4.73; 7.8532046; \dots \quad (5)$$

Qistirilgan tomonlari uchun β_i larni aniqlash imkonini beruvchi tenglamani hosil qilamiz.

$$\begin{aligned} & (\beta_i^2 + \mu\lambda)(\cosh(\beta_i b) - \cos(\beta_i b))(\beta_i^2 + (2 - \mu)\lambda)(\cosh(\beta_i b) + \cos(\beta_i b)) - \\ & - \left((\beta_i^2 + \mu\lambda) \sinh(\beta_i b) + \frac{(-\beta_i^2 + \mu\lambda)(\beta_i^2 + (2 - \mu)\lambda)}{-\beta_i^2 + (2 - \mu)\lambda} \sin(\beta_i b) \right) \times \\ & \times \left((\beta_i^2 + (2 - \mu)\lambda) \sinh(\beta_i b) + \frac{(\beta_i^2 + \mu\lambda)(\beta_i^2 - (2 - \mu)\lambda)}{-\beta_i^2 + \mu\lambda} \sin(\beta_i b) \right) = 0, \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

bunda μ – Puasson koeffitsiyenti; $\lambda = \frac{1}{X_i(x)} \frac{\partial^2 X_i(x)}{\partial x^2}$; b – plastinka tomoni.

(6) tenglama β_i larni aniqlash imkonini beradi.

(6) tenglamani plastinka materiali po‘lat bo‘lgan hol uchun grafik usulda yechamiz. U holda, $\mu = 0.3$; $E = 2.08 \cdot 10^{11} \frac{N}{m^2}$; $\rho = 7810 \frac{kg}{m^3}$; $\alpha_i a = 4.73$;

Plastinkaning tomonlari $a = b = 0.44 \text{ m}$ bo‘lsin. U holda $\lambda = -115.5625$.

(6) tenglamaning grafigini chizamiz.

2-rasm. (6) chastotani aniqlash imkonini beruvchi tenglama grafigi (a) va uning nollari (b,c)

2-rasmda (6) chastotani aniqlash imkonini beruvchi tenglama grafigi (a) va uning nollari (b, c) tasvirlangan. Bu garfikdan (6) tenglamani qanoatlantiruvchi β_i ning noldan farqli dastlabki ikkita qiymatlarini quyidagicha aniqlash mumkin:

$$\beta_i = 3.1788126; 7.1399833; \dots \quad (7)$$

Natijalar va ularning muhokamasi.

Olingan tenglamalar asosida xususiy chastotani aniqlaymiz.

Plastinka qalinligini $h = 0.005 \text{ m}$ deb olsak, u holda

$$D = \frac{Eh^3}{12(1-\mu^2)} = \frac{2.08 \cdot 10^{11} \frac{N}{m^2} \cdot 5^3 \cdot 10^{-9} m^3}{12(1-3^2 \cdot 10^{-2})} = 2470 \text{ Nm.}$$

Natijada xususiy chastotani aniqlaymiz.

$$p_{11} = 999.4484832 \text{ s}^{-1}.$$

To‘g‘ri to‘rtburchak shaklidagi plastinkaning xususiy chastotalari aniqlashning analitik ifodalari, uning tebranish xususiyatlari batafsil o‘rganish imkonini beradi. Qarama-qarshi tomonlarning qistirib mahkamlanganligi plastinkaning umumiy qattiqligini oshirishi, qolgan ikki tomonning erkin bo‘lishi esa tebranish shakllarining xilma-xilligini ta‘minlaydi. Chegaraviy shartlar yechimning xarakterini belgilab, xususiy chastotalarning qiymatiga sezilarli ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi. Xususiy chastotalarning plastinkaning geometrik o‘lchamlari hamda material xossalriga bevosita bog‘liq ekanligi ko‘rsatadi. Olingan natijalar plastinkaning tebranish formalarini aniqlash imkonini berib, har bir formalar uning ma‘lum shaklda deformatsiyalanishini ifodalashini ko‘rsatadi.

Xulosa. Kinematik qo‘zg‘alishlar ta‘siridagi qarama qarshi tomonlari qistirib mahkamlangan va qolgan ikki tomonlari erkin bo‘lgan to‘g‘ri to‘rtburchak shaklidagi plastinkaning xususiy chastotalari aniqlandi. Xususiy tebranish formalari trigonometrik va giperbolik funksiyalardan iborat funksiyalar ko‘rinishida izlanib, ularning koeffitsiyentlari asosida α_i va β_i **transsendent tenglama ildizlarini aniqlash imkonini beruvchi tenglamalar olindi. Olingan natijalar sonli hisoblashlar asosida tahlil qilindi.**

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